

Religion in the Early Bronze Age / Canaan

also known as "Religion in the Early Bronze Age / southern Levant"

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Entry tags: Syro-Palestinian Religion, Ancient Mediterranean, Early Bronze Age, Religious Group, Canaanite Religions, Southern Levant, Temple Buildings and Temple Cult, Semitic, West Semitic, Language, Canaanite, Northwest Semitic, Afro-Asiatic, Central Semitic

Given the absence of written sources, evidence of cult and religion in Canaan / southern Levant during the Early Bronze Age (3600–2400 BCE) relies exclusively on the material remains that people inhabiting this region have left behind. These material remains are limited and the interpretation of their meaning often remains uncertain. Religious architecture represents the main evidence for the period, with the classic type of the broad-room temple, placed in a courtyard at times equipped with a stone altar for sacrifices. In addition, a few cult objects (cultic vessels, shrine models, figurines) and some iconographic sources, i.e. cylindrical seals decorated with cult scenes, shed light on some cultic practices and rituals. The cylinder seals impressions, in particular, seem to indicate the practice of a fertility cult, linked to a fertility goddess who represented the main deity. Early Bronze Age temples may have been dedicated to this fertility goddess. On the other hand, the presence of twin temples – as in the sacred area of Arad – could indicate the worship of a divine couple (possibly depicted also on some EB III cylinder seal impressions), with a male deity worshipped as a partner of the fertility goddess. The increasing images of bulls documented in the Early Bronze Age may be associated with this male deity (a prototype of El, Baal or Dagan in the second millennium BCE). The temples were also to be the center of cultic events and public rituals involving the members of the community.

Date Range: 3600 BCE - 2400 BCE

Region: Canaan

Region tags: Canaan, southern Levant

The area of the southern Levant as defined at least from the mid-2nd millennium BCE based on historical sources. It corresponds to the territory presently occupied by the modern states of Israel, the West Bank and Gaza, Jordan, and the southern portions of Syria and Lebanon.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: de Miroschedji, Pierre. 2011. At the Origin of Canaanite Cult and Religion: the Early Bronze Age Fertility Ritual in Palestine. *Eretz Israel* 30 (Ben-Tor Volume), pp. 74*-103*.
- Source 2: Sala, Maura. 2008. *L'architettura sacra della Palestina nell'età del Bronzo Antico I-III (Contributi e Materiali di Archeologia Orientale XIII)*. Rome: Sapienza Università di Roma.
- Source 3: de Miroschedji, Pierre. 1993. Cult and Religion in the Chalcolithic and Early Bronze Age. In A.

Biran and J. Aviram (eds.), *Biblical Archaeology Today*, 1990: Proceedings of the Second International Congress on Biblical Archaeology, Jerusalem, June-July 1990. Jerusalem: Israel Exploration Society, pp. 208-220.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (unknown relationship to other religious groups, or presence of other religious groups unknown)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Written sources are not attested in the southern Levant throughout the late fourth and third millennium BCE.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Reference: Sala, Maura. *L'architettura Sacra Della Palestina Nell'età Del Bronzo Antico I-III (contributi E Materiali Di Archeologia Orientale XIII)*. Rome: Sapienza Università di Roma, 2008.

Reference: Kempinski, Aharon. “Chalcolithic and Early Bronze Age Temples”. In *The Architecture of Ancient Israel: From the Prehistoric to the Persian Periods*, edited by Aharon Kempinski and Ronny Reich. Jerusalem: Israel Exploration Society, 1992.

In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In general, only limited portions of the Early Bronze Age settlements have been

excavated, therefore it is not possible to establish the percentage of the area taken up by the religious monuments. An exception is represented by the site of Tel Arad (in the northern Negev) during the Early Bronze II: the extension of the sacred precinct (920 square meters) with respect to the area surrounded by the city-walls (about 10 hectares) corresponds to about 10% (Early Arad II, pp. 45–63, 142–143).

Reference: Ruth, Amiran, and Ornit Ilan. *Early Arad II: The Chalcolithic and Early Bronze IB Settlements and the Early Bronze II City: Architecture and Town Planning: Sixth to Eighteenth Seasons of Excavations, 1971-1978, 1980-1984*. Jerusalem: The Israel Museum and Israel Exploration Society, 1996.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 1100

Notes: The Great Temple of Stratum XVIII/Level J-4 at Megiddo: a broad-room building, 47.5 × 22.0 m in size, including the rectangular temple hall and two corridors extending at the back. A row of 10 stone slabs serving as column bases lies at the center of the hall. An altar is situated against the back wall facing the entrance, while twelve huge basalt offering tables embedded in the floor extend in two rows across the temple hall. All the walls of the building are about 3.5 m thick. An original height of up to 4 m for the walls has been hypothesized. The rich faunal assemblage from the rear corridors sheds light on the sacrificial procedures performed in the sanctuary. In addition, huge amounts of ash and bones were found across the large open area south of the temple, suggesting that this space was used for intense ritual activity (e.g., sacrifice preparation and feasting). <https://megiddoexpedition.wordpress.com/present-excavation/#jp-carousel-451> <https://megiddoexpedition.wordpress.com/present-excavation/#jp-carousel-452> <https://megiddoexpedition.wordpress.com/present-excavation/#jp-carousel-453>

Reference: Ussishkin, David. "The Sacred Area of Early Bronze Megiddo: History and Interpretation". *Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental Research* 373 (May 1, 2015): 69–104. <https://doi.org/10.5615/bullamerschoorie.373.0069>.

Reference: Adams, Matthew J., Israel Finkelstein, and David Ussishkin. "The Great Temple of Early Bronze I Megiddo". *American Journal of Archaeology* 118, no. 2 (April 1, 2014): 285–305. <https://doi.org/10.3764/aja.118.2.0285>.

Reference: Finkelstein, Israel, David Ussishkin, and Eric H. Cline. *Megiddo V: The 2004–2008 Seasons* (monograph Series of the Sonia and Marco Nadler Institute of Archaeology 31). Penn State University Press, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.5325/j.ctv2321hmw>.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Buildings are not preserved with their original elevation. An original height of up to 4 m has been hypothesized for the Great Temple of Stratum XVIII/Level J-4 at Megiddo.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Monuments have very variable dimensions.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Buildings are not preserved with their original elevation.

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Archaeologists typically find adult burials in rock-cut tombs (cave tombs). Simple pit and cist burials are sometimes recorded. In some parts of the country other burial structures were adopted: dolmens (mainly on the east side of the Jordan Valley) and cist burials covered by tumuli (in the Negev and Transjordan). A very special case is represented by the above-surface charnel houses at the Jordanian site of Bab edh-Dhra.

Reference: Ilan, David. "Mortuary Practices in Early Bronze Age Canaan". *Near Eastern Archaeology* 65, no. 2 (April 21, 2002). <https://doi.org/10.2307/3210870>.

Reference: Schaub, Thomas R.. *Bâb Edh-bhrâ: Excavations in the Cemetery Directed by Paul W. Lapp (1965-67) (reports of the Expedition to the Dead Sea Plain, Jordan, Vol. 1)*. Edited by Walter E. Rast. Winona Lake, IN: Eisenbrauns, 1989.

Reference: Kenyon, Kathleen. *Excavations at Jericho. Volume One. The Tombs Excavated in 1952-4*. London: The British School of Archaeology in Jerusalem, 1960.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Reference: Ilan, David. "Mortuary Practices in Early Bronze Age Canaan". *Near Eastern Archaeology* 65, no. 2 (April 21, 2002). <https://doi.org/10.2307/3210870>.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Reference: Kempinski, Aharon. "Chalcolithic and Early Bronze Age Temples". In *The Architecture of Ancient Israel: From the Prehistoric to the Persian Periods*, edited by Aharon Kempinski and Ronny Reich. Jerusalem: Israel Exploration Society, 1992.

Reference: Sala, Maura. *L'architettura Sacra Della Palestina Nell'età Del Bronzo Antico I-III (contributi E Materiali Di Archeologia Orientale XIII)*. Rome: Sapienza Università di Roma, 2008.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: See, for instance, Round Altar 4017 at Megiddo. Many animal bones were uncovered in the debris surrounding the altar, evidence of sacrificial activities.
<https://www.bibleplaces.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Megiddo-Early-Bronze-sacrificial-altar-aerial-tbs120360011.jpg>

↳ Devotional markers:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: neighborhood shrines/domestic chapels

Notes: small shrines/chapels directly inserted in the residential areas; e.g. at Tell es-Sultan (shrine 420; Early Bronze I), Tell el-Far'ah North (shrine 671; Early Bronze II), and Khirbet Kerak (shrine of layer XA; Early Bronze III)

Reference: Sala, Maura. *L'architettura Sacra Della Palestina Nell'età Del Bronzo Antico I-III (contributi E Materiali Di Archeologia Orientale XIII)*. Rome: Sapienza Università di Roma, 2008.

– Yes [specify]: megalithic mortuary structures

Notes: Dolmen fields mainly on the east side of the Jordan Valley, in the second half of the fourth millennium BCE. See, for instance, the Damiya Dolmen Field.

<https://www.wmf.org/project/damiya-dolmen-field#:~:text=In%20the%20lower%20foothills%20of,burial%20chambers%20known%20as%20dolmen>

<https://www.wmf.org/project/damiya-dolmen-field#:~:text=In%20the%20lower%20foothills%20of,burial%20chambers%20known%20as%20dolmen>

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: Iconography is mainly documented by cult scenes depicted on cylinder seal impressions and a few cult vessels (from Tel Beth Yerah and Tel Yarmouth). Worth mentioning are the graffiti scratched on the pavement in front of the EB IB temple at Megiddo, and the cult stele from Tel Arad in the EB II.

Reference: de Miroschedji, Pierre. "At the Origin of Canaanite Cult and Religion: The Early Bronze Age Fertility Ritual in Palestine". *Eretz-israel: Archaeological, Historical and Geographical Studies* 30 (January 1, 2011): 74*-103*. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23631005>.

Reference: Amiran, Ruth. "A Cult Stele from Arad". *Israel Exploration Journal* 22, no. 2/3 (January 1, 1972): 86-88. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/27925332>.

Reference: de Miroschedji, Pierre. "La Glyptique Palestinienne Du Bronze Ancien". In *De Chypre À La Bactriane, Les Sceaux Du Proche-orient Ancien. Actes Du Colloque International Organisé Au Musée Du Louvre Par Le Service Culturel Le 18 Mars 1995, À Edith Porada in Memoriam, 189-209*. Paris: La Documentation Française, 1997.

Reference: Ben-Tor, Ammon. "Cult Scenes on Early Bronze Age Cylinder Seal Impressions from Palestine". *Levant* 9, no. 1 (January 1, 1977): 90-100. <https://doi.org/10.1179/lev.1977.9.1.90>.

Reference: Ben-Tor, Ammon. "New Light on Cylinder Seal Impressions Showing Cult Scenes from Early Bronze Age Palestine". *Israel Exploration Journal* 42, no. 3/4 (May 1, 1992): 153–64. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/27926268>.

Reference: Ussishkin, David. "The Sacred Area of Early Bronze Megiddo: History and Interpretation". *Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental Research* 373 (May 1, 2015): 69–104. <https://doi.org/10.5615/bullamerschoorie.373.0069>.

Reference: Loud, Gordon. *Megiddo II. Seasons of 1935–39* (oriental Institute Publications 62). Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1948. <https://oi.uchicago.edu/research/publications/oip/oip-62-megiddo-2-seasons-1935%E2%80%9339-text-and-plates>.

Reference: Amiran, Ruth. "Re-examination of a Cult-and-art Object from Beth Yerah". In *Essays in Ancient Civilization Presented to Helene J. Kantor* (studies in Ancient Oriental Civilization 47), edited by Albert Leonard Jr. and Bruce Beyer Williams, 31–33. Chicago: The Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago, 1989. <https://oi.uchicago.edu/research/publications/saoc/saoc-47-essays-ancient-civilization-presented-helene-j-kantor>.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- At home
- Only religious public space
- Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Humans:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Field doesn't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It has been suggested that the Megiddo temples during the late fourth millennium BCE (EB IB) could serve as a pilgrimage site for people from the surrounding region. In fact, the regional survey carried out by the Megiddo Expedition in the Jezreel Valley revealed an extensive settlement in this region during the EB IB.

Reference: Ussishkin, David. "The Sacred Area of Early Bronze Megiddo: History and Interpretation". *Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental Research* 373 (May 1, 2015): 69-104. <https://doi.org/10.5615/bullamerschoorie.373.0069>.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The grave goods and the treatment of the bones seem to suggest a belief in afterlife.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Determining situations of sacrifice is very difficult based on the archaeological evidence.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– No

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: E.g., stone vessels, metal weapons, jewelry made of semiprecious stones, faience, silver and copper. Very few gold jewels are also attested.

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Imported objects (e.g., Egyptian imports).

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: Mainly pottery vessels.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

- ↳ As cenotaphs:
 - No
- ↳ In cemetery:
 - Yes
- ↳ Family tomb-crypt:
 - No
- ↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):
 - No
- ↳ Other formal burial type:
 - Yes [specify]: Tumuli and dolmen fields

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

- ↳ A supreme high god is present:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: In the absence of written sources, it is difficult to reconstruct which supernatural beings were worshiped. Based on some iconographic representations (e.g., cult scenes depicted on cylindrical seals and a terracotta shrine model from Tel Yarmuth), it has been suggested that a fertility ritual, linked to a great fertility goddess, played a central role. Early Bronze Age temples may have been dedicated to this fertility goddess. The presence of twin temples(?), as in the sacred area of Arad, could also indicate the worship of a divine couple, with a male deity worshiped as a partner of the fertility goddess. The increasing images of bulls could be associated with this male deity, a prototype of El, Baal or Dagan (depending on the region) in the second millennium BCE. Indeed, in the second millennium BCE this male deity will take on a preeminent role.

Reference: de Miroschedji, Pierre. "La Glyptique Palestinienne Du Bronze Ancien". In *De Chypre À La Bactriane, Les Sceaux Du Proche-orient Ancien. Actes Du Colloque International Organisé Au Musée Du Louvre Par Le Service Culturel Le 18 Mars 1995, À Edith Porada in Memoriam, 189-209*. Paris: La Documentation Française, 1997.

Reference: de Miroschedji, Pierre. "À Propos D'un Fragment D'objet En Forme De Construction: Un Aspect Des Pratiques Cultuelles Cananéennes Aux Âges Du Bronze Et Du Fer". In *Profils*

D'objets, Approches D'anthropologues Et D'archéologues (colloques De La Maison René-ginouès 7), edited by F. Wateau, C. Perlès, and P. Soulier, 109–20. Paris: De Boccard, 2011.

Reference: de Miroschedji, Pierre. "At the Origin of Canaanite Cult and Religion: The Early Bronze Age Fertility Ritual in Palestine". *Eretz-israel: Archaeological, Historical and Geographical Studies* 30 (January 1, 2011): 74*-103*. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23631005>.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Field doesn't know

Is an eschatology present:

– Field doesn't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: There is no archaeological evidence of this.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: There is no archaeological evidence of this.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: There is no archaeological evidence of this.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: Based on some cult scenes depicted on cylinder seal impressions, the existence of ceremonies that periodically assembled the community for the accomplishment of a fertility ritual has been suggested.

Reference: de Miroschedji, Pierre. "At the Origin of Canaanite Cult and Religion: The Early Bronze Age Fertility Ritual in Palestine". *Eretz-israel: Archaeological, Historical and Geographical Studies* 30 (January 1, 2011): 74*-103*. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23631005>.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The Early Bronze Age in the southern Levant witnesses the transition from a village-based organization (in the Early Bronze I) to the first urbanized society in the region (in the Early Bronze II-III), organized in a system of fortified towns probably controlling the surrounding territory and villages.

Reference: Greenberg, Raphael. *The Archaeology of the Bronze Age Levant*. Cambridge University Press, 2019. https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Archaeology_of_the_Bronze_Age_Levant.html?hl=&id=wi2xDwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Steiner, Margreet L., and Ann E. Killebrew. *The Oxford Handbook of the Archaeology of the Levant*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2014. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=B29oAgAAQBAJ>.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Written sources are not attested in the southern Levant throughout the late fourth and third millennium BCE

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Written sources are not attested in the southern Levant throughout the late fourth and third millennium BCE

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Written sources are not attested in the southern Levant throughout the late fourth and third millennium BCE

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Field doesn't know

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Religion in the Early Bronze Age / Canaan, Sala, Maura. *L'architettura Sacra Della Palestina Nell'età Del Bronzo Antico I-III (contributi E Materiali Di Archeologia Orientale XIII)*. Rome: Sapienza Università di Roma, 2008.

Reference: Religion in the Early Bronze Age / Canaan, Amiran, Ruth. "A Cult Stele from Arad". *Israel Exploration Journal* 22, no. 2/3 (January 1, 1972): 86-88. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/27925332>.

Reference: Religion in the Early Bronze Age / Canaan, de Miroschedji, Pierre. "Cult and Religion in the Chalcolithic and Early Bronze Age". In *Biblical Archaeology Today, 1990: Proceedings of the Second International Congress on Biblical Archaeology, Jerusalem, June-july 1990*, edited by Avraham Biran and Joseph Aviram, 208-20. Jerusalem: Israel Exploration Society, 1993.

Reference: Religion in the Early Bronze Age / Canaan, de Miroschedji, Pierre. "At the Origin of Canaanite Cult and Religion: The Early Bronze Age Fertility Ritual in Palestine". *Eretz-israel: Archaeological, Historical and Geographical Studies* 30 (January 1, 2011): 74*-103*. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23631005>.

Reference: Religion in the Early Bronze Age / Canaan, Sala, Maura. "Sanctuaries, Temples and Cult Places in Early Bronze I Southern Levant". *Vicino & Medio Oriente* 15 (January 1, 2011): 1-32. http://www.journal-vo.it/Pubblicazioni/V&MO%20XV/V&MO_XV_Sala.pdf.

Reference: Religion in the Early Bronze Age / Canaan, Kempinski, Aharon. "Chalcolithic and Early Bronze Age Temples". In *The Architecture of Ancient Israel: From the Prehistoric to the Persian Periods*, edited by Aharon Kempinski and Ronny Reich. Jerusalem: Israel Exploration Society, 1992.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Yes, Kempinski, Aharon. "Chalcolithic and Early Bronze Age Temples". In *The Architecture of Ancient Israel: From the Prehistoric to the Persian Periods*, edited by Aharon Kempinski and Ronny Reich. Jerusalem: Israel Exploration Society, 1992.

Reference: Yes, Sala, Maura. *L'architettura Sacra Della Palestina Nell'età Del Bronzo Antico I-III (contributi E Materiali Di Archeologia Orientale XIII)*. Rome: Sapienza Università di Roma, 2008. , ,

Reference: Yes, Amiran, Ruth. "A Cult Stele from Arad". *Israel Exploration Journal* 22, no. 2/3 (January 1, 1972): 86-88. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/27925332>.

Reference: Yes, Amiran, Ruth. "Re-examination of a Cult-and-art Object from Beth Yerah". In *Essays in Ancient Civilization Presented to Helene J. Kantor (studies in Ancient Oriental Civilization 47)*, edited by Albert Leonard Jr. and Bruce Beyer Williams, 31-33. Chicago: The Oriental Institute of the University of

Chicago, 1989. <https://oi.uchicago.edu/research/publications/saoc/saoc-47-essays-ancient-civilization-presented-helene-j-kantor>.

Reference: Yes, Ben-Tor, Ammon. "Cult Scenes on Early Bronze Age Cylinder Seal Impressions from Palestine". *Levant* 9, no. 1 (January 1, 1977): 90-100. <https://doi.org/10.1179/lev.1977.9.1.90>.

Reference: Yes, de Miroschedji, Pierre. "At the Origin of Canaanite Cult and Religion: The Early Bronze Age Fertility Ritual in Palestine". *Eretz-israel: Archaeological, Historical and Geographical Studies* 30 (January 1, 2011): 74*-103*. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23631005>. , ,

Reference: Square meters: 1100, Ussishkin, David. "The Sacred Area of Early Bronze Megiddo: History and Interpretation". *Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental Research* 373 (May 1, 2015): 69-104. <https://doi.org/10.5615/bullamerschoorie.373.0069>.

Reference: Square meters: 1100, Adams, Matthew J., Israel Finkelstein, and David Ussishkin. "The Great Temple of Early Bronze I Megiddo". *American Journal of Archaeology* 118, no. 2 (April 1, 2014): 285-305. <https://doi.org/10.3764/aja.118.2.0285>.

Reference: Field doesn't know, Ussishkin, David. "The Sacred Area of Early Bronze Megiddo: History and Interpretation". *Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental Research* 373 (May 1, 2015): 69-104. <https://doi.org/10.5615/bullamerschoorie.373.0069>.

Reference: Square meters: 1100, Finkelstein, Israel, David Ussishkin, and Eric H. Cline. *Megiddo V: The 2004-2008 Seasons* (monograph Series of the Sonia and Marco Nadler Institute of Archaeology 31). Penn State University Press, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.5325/j.ctv2321hmw>.

Reference: Field doesn't know, Ruth, Amiran, and Ornit Ilan. *Early Arad II: The Chalcolithic and Early Bronze IB Settlements and the Early Bronze II City: Architecture and Town Planning: Sixth to Eighteenth Seasons of Excavations, 1971-1978, 1980-1984*. Jerusalem: The Israel Museum and Israel Exploration Society, 1996.

Reference: Other [specify in comments], Greenberg, Raphael. *The Archaeology of the Bronze Age Levant*. Cambridge University Press, 2019. https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Archaeology_of_the_Bronze_Age_Levant.html?hl=&id=wi2xDwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Other [specify in comments], Steiner, Margreet L., and Ann E. Killebrew. *The Oxford Handbook of the Archaeology of the Levant*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2014. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=B29oAgAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Yes, Ilan, David. "Mortuary Practices in Early Bronze Age Canaan". *Near Eastern Archaeology* 65, no. 2 (April 21, 2002). <https://doi.org/10.2307/3210870>. ,

Reference: Yes, de Miroschedji, Pierre. "La Glyptique Palestinienne Du Bronze Ancien". In *De Chypre À La Bactriane, Les Sceaux Du Proche-orient Ancien. Actes Du Colloque International Organisé Au Musée Du Louvre Par Le Service Culturel Le 18 Mars 1995, À Edith Porada in Memoriam, 189-209*. Paris: La Documentation Française, 1997.

Reference: Yes, de Miroschedji, Pierre. "À Propos D'un Fragment D'objet En Forme De Construction: Un Aspect Des Pratiques Culturelles Cananéennes Aux Âges Du Bronze Et Du Fer". In *Profils D'objets, Approches D'anthropologues Et D'archéologues (colloques De La Maison René-ginouvs 7)*, edited by F. Wateau, C. Perlès, and P. Soulier, 109-20. Paris: De Boccard, 2011.

Reference: Yes, de Miroschedji, Pierre. "La Glyptique Palestinienne Du Bronze Ancien". In *De Chypre À La Bactriane, Les Sceaux Du Proche-orient Ancien. Actes Du Colloque International Organisé Au Musée Du Louvre Par Le Service Culturel Le 18 Mars 1995, À Edith Porada in Memoriam, 189-209*. Paris: La Documentation Française, 1997.

Reference: Yes, Ben-Tor, Ammon. "New Light on Cylinder Seal Impressions Showing Cult Scenes from Early Bronze Age Palestine". *Israel Exploration Journal* 42, no. 3/4 (May 1, 1992): 153-64. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/27926268>.

Reference: Yes, Ussishkin, David. "The Sacred Area of Early Bronze Megiddo: History and Interpretation". *Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental Research* 373 (May 1, 2015): 69-104. <https://doi.org/10.5615/bullamerschoorie.373.0069>.

Reference: Yes, Loud, Gordon. *Megiddo II. Seasons of 1935-39* (oriental Institute Publications 62). Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1948. <https://oi.uchicago.edu/research/publications/oip/oip-62-megiddo-2-seasons-1935%E2%80%9339-text-and-plates>.

Reference: Yes, Kempinski, Aharon. "Chalcolithic and Early Bronze Age Temples". In *The Architecture of Ancient Israel: From the Prehistoric to the Persian Periods*, edited by Aharon Kempinski and Ronny Reich. Jerusalem: Israel Exploration Society, 1992.

Reference: Yes, Schaub, Thomas R. *Bâb Edh-bhrâ: Excavations in the Cemetery Directed by Paul W. Lapp (1965-67)* (reports of the Expedition to the Dead Sea Plain, Jordan, Vol. 1). Edited by Walter E. Rast. Winona Lake, IN: Eisenbrauns, 1989.

Reference: Yes, Kenyon, Kathleen. *Excavations at Jericho. Volume One. The Tombs Excavated in 1952-4*. London: The British School of Archaeology in Jerusalem, 1960.